

IRISCC

D8.1

Optimized IRISCC TA management tool

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Abstract

Key words

Access management, process, workflow, application, review, feasibility

This document describes the DEM- Optimized Transnational Access management tool delivered with IRISCC Deliverable D8.1. The tool allows for centralised management of the physical, remote, and hybrid access provision in the frame of the IRISCC project.

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V 1.1	4/02/2025	Revision of v1.0	Davide Di Cioccio (EMBRC) Päivi Haapanala (LUKE)
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V 3.0	15/05/2025	Submitted version	Rosa Maria Petracca Altieri and the ACTRIS SAMU Team (CNR)

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D8.1 Optimized IRISCC TA management tool

Work Package Number 8

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Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
Access	The legitimate and authorised physical, remote and virtual admission to, interactions with and use of Research Infrastructures and to services offered by Research Infrastructures to users
PASS	Platform for managing user Access to ACTRIS Services (PASS), an online, centralised access management platform operated by the ACTRIS Service and Access Management Unit and made available to IRISCC to manage physical, remote and hybrid access to the research facilities.
SAMU	Service and Access Management Unit of the ACTRIS ERIC Head Office
TA	Transnational access (physical, remote, hybrid)
<i>TA - Physical access</i>	Physical access is “hands-on” access when users physically visit an infrastructure/facility/equipment/installation. Physical access means access to services offered by IRISCC through an installation of the participating RIs. The available services or resources are not unlimited, and a competitive, peer-reviewed process is required following a defined procedure with well-defined criteria and call conditions for the selection of users.
<i>TA - Remote access</i>	Remote access is access to resources and services offered by IRISCC through participating RIs without users physically visiting the infrastructure/facility/equipment/installation. Similar to physical access, the services or resources are not unlimited, and a competitive, peer-reviewed process is required following a defined procedure with well-defined criteria and call conditions for the selection of users.
<i>TA - Hybrid access</i>	Hybrid access combines multiple types of access to IRISCC resources and services, including virtual, physical and remote access. As hybrid involves resources for which the IRISCC facilities have limited capacity, a competitive selection of users similar to that described above for physical and remote access is required.
User	A person, a team, or an institution from any sector, including the public and private sector, making use of RI data or other services, including access to the RI facilities.
WP	Work Package, a component of the project work breakdown representing a manageable unit of work within a project, including a major group of project activities targeting common specific objectives.

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Executive summary

PASS (Platform for managing user access to ACTRIS ServiceS) is the access management platform optimised to enable and ease the management of the Transnational Access (TA) process in the frame of the IRISCC project.

Implemented as a web tool by the Service and Access Management Unit of the ACTRIS Head Office (SAMU), leader of IRISCC Work Package 8 “IRISCC TA and VA access management”, PASS has been made available to IRISCC. The existing tool has been customised to organise and control the central management and selection of user requests to access services provided by the facilities/platforms/installations via IRISCC.

The customised PASS for IRISCC was initially released in November 2024 as described in project’s internal Milestone 10 – 1st release of the optimised TA management tool. It was then updated following the reviews of the application form and the review forms received until March 2025 (version v2.0). Final optimisation of the PASS to accommodate the management of the Strategic IRISCC Access Programme as described in Deliverable D7.2 – Strategic IRISCC Access Programme was done in April 2025 (version v3.0).

The web tool PASS can be reached at <https://passactris.smapply.io> and potential applicants can access it via a link from the IRISCC Catalogue of Services released in April 2025 – the single-entry point for IRISCC services.

This report of the Deliverable D8.1 “Optimized IRISCC TA management tool” (DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype) does not describe in detail the workflow or technicalities of the customisations made on the PASS but offers views to the web interface. It shares screen shots of the PASS homepage, the IRISCC TA Calls programme including the IRISCC TA Call for Fast-Track, and the TA admin, applicant and the reviewer portals. The IRISCC TA admin portal and dashboard allow management of different calls/programs in parallel.

1. Introduction

PASS (Platform for managing user access to ACTRIS ServiceS) is the access management platform optimised to enable and ease the management of the Transnational Access (TA) process in the frame of the IRISCC project. PASS can be reached at <https://passactris.smapply.io> and potential applicants are directed to PASS via a link from the IRISCC Catalogue of Services released in April – the one access point for IRISCC services.

Implemented as a web tool by the Service and Access Management Unit of the ACTRIS Head Office (SAMU), leader of IRISCC Work Package 8 “IRISCC TA and VA access management”, PASS has been made available to IRISCC. An existing tool has been customised to organise and control the central management and selection of user requests to access services provided by the facilities/platforms/installations via IRISCC.

The customised PASS for IRISCC was initially released in November 2024 and described in project’s internal Milestone 10 - 1st release of the optimised TA management tool [R1]. It was then updated following the reviews of the TA application form and the TA review forms received until March 2025 and finally optimised to accommodate the management of the Strategic IRISCC Access Programme as described in Deliverable D7.2 – Strategic IRISCC Access Programme [R2] published in April 2025.

The sections below offer some views to the PASS homepage and the IRISCC TA Calls programme and the related workflows (Section 2), the TA admin portal and dashboard allowing management of different calls/programs in parallel (Section 3), the TA applicant portal (Section 4) and the TA reviewer portal (Section 5).

2. IRISCC TA Calls Programme

A dedicated TA Calls programme has been designed, developed, and implemented on PASS to ensure the management of TA calls published during the IRISCC project, following the process, roles, and criteria agreed upon by the IRISCC Executive Board.

Figure 1 provides a screenshot of the PASS homepage featuring the access programmes available to users. Figure 2 provides a screenshot of the IRISCC Access programme available for user applications via PASS. Figure 3 shows all the steps in the customised workflow for the IRISCC TA process management.

ACTRIS PASS - Platform for managing user access to ACTRIS Services

ACTRIS PASS (Platform for managing user access to ACTRIS Services) is a web tool designed and implemented by the Service and Access Management Unit of the ACTRIS Head Office. It provides a collection of services to all the users involved in the process of submitting, managing and reviewing the requests to access physical and remote services provided by the ACTRIS facilities distributed in Europe and by the other research infrastructures partnering with ACTRIS under specific projects.

How to Apply

ACTRIS offers different options to access physical and remote services, open and limited and with different application process.

Explore the available programs below, and start your application today!

Programs

Search programs..

IRISCC Access Programme: 1st TA Call

Accepting applications from Apr 22 2025 12:00 (CEST) to Jun 11 2025 17:00 (CEST)

The IRISCC TA Calls Programme will provide access to scientific and knowledge services enabling in-depth understanding of climate change-driven risks

[MORE >](#)

IRISCC TA Fast Track Call

Accepting applications from Apr 22 2025 12:00 (CEST) to Dec 31 2025 17:00 (CET)

The IRISCC TA Fast Track Call provides access to IRISCC scientific and knowledge services through an accelerated and streamlined procedure especially designed for urgent needs and Ukrainian users.

[MORE >](#)

Figure 1. Screenshot of the PASS Homepage.

IRISCC Access Programme: 1st TA Call

The IRISCC TA calls programme will support access to several diverse and complementary leading research infrastructures (RIs) across different domains and sectors, from natural sciences to social sciences, to foster cutting-edge research and evidence-based policymaking for improving Europe's resilience to climate change.

IRISCC provides scientific and knowledge services that enable an in-depth understanding of climate change-driven risks, including their determinants (hazards, exposure, and vulnerabilities) and impacts on human, production, and natural systems.

The TA programme will integrate various modalities of access—physical, remote, and hybrid—and reflect the strategic development of IRISCC services to increasingly include an updated range of services for research tackling climate change risks.

The 1st TA call will open in Spring 2025.

STAY TUNED!

Opens
April 2025

Deadline
June 2025

Categories
IRISCC

Figure 2. Screenshot of the PASS: IRISCC Access Programme – 1st TA Call.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the PASS: IRISCC TA call management workflow.

Figure 4 provides a screenshot of the IRISCC Fast-Track programme available for user applications via PASS. It is a rolling call permanently open to collect, at any time, access requests:

- coming from **Ukrainian researchers**
- with **convincingly urgent scientific cases** (i.e., environmental crises, extreme events or other emergencies that require a quick scientific reaction).

The Fast-Track call provides a faster and more streamlined process to access the services of the diverse and complementary leading research infrastructures (RIs) involved in IRISCC and operating in different domains and sectors, from natural sciences to social sciences.

IRISCC TA Fast Track Call

The IRISCC TA Fast Track Call is a rolling call permanently open to collect at any time access requests:

- coming from **Ukrainian researchers**
- with **convincingly urgent scientific cases** (i.e., environmental crises, extreme events or other emergencies that require a quick scientific reaction).

The call provides a faster and more streamlined process to access the services of the diverse and complementary leading research infrastructures (RIs) involved in IRISCC and operating in different domains and sectors, from natural sciences to social sciences.

IRISCC scientific and knowledge services enable an in-depth understanding of climate change-driven risks, including their determinants (hazards, exposure, and vulnerabilities) and impacts on human, production, and natural systems.

The TA Fast Track Call will open in Spring 2025.

STAY TUNED!

Opens
April 2025

Deadline
Dec 31 2025 17:00 (CET)

Categories
IRISCC

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Figure 4. Screenshot of the PASS: IRISCC Fast-Track Call.

3. TA admin portal

Figure 5 provides a screenshot of the TA admin portal where the IRISCC WP8 TA Management Team/SAMU can manage and monitor all the ongoing user, provider and reviewer activities under the different calls and extract reports.

Figure 5. Screenshot of the PASS: IRISCC TA admin portal.

4. TA User portal

Figure 6 provides a screenshot of the TA user portal where the users can see all their applications, in preparation and submitted, and complete the relevant tasks when requested.

Figure 6. Screenshot of the PASS: IRISCC TA User portal.

5. TA Reviewer portal

Figure 7 provides a screenshot of the TA reviewer portal where providers and reviewers can see all the applications they have assigned and complete the feasibility check or peer review when requested.

Figure 7. Screenshot of the PASS: IRISCC TA Reviewer portal.

6. References

Reference	
No	Description/Link
R1.	IRISCC Milestone MS10 - 1st release of the optimized TA management tool. Project's internal document.
R2.	S. Philippin, P. Haapanala, R. M. Petracca Altieri, A. Dobust, M. Oliveri: Strategic IRISCC Access Programme, IRISCC Deliverable D7.2. 10.5281/zenodo.15102251